

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 1 AUGUST 2019
Available at: www.naspublishers.com

ISSN 2321-5453

INNOVATIVE THOUGHTS

INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL

nas
PUBLISHERS

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF EUNUCHS (TRANSGENDER)

Atul Gautam¹ and Prof. J. P. Dubey²

Abstract
Eunuchs being one of the most marginalized sections of the society in India, don't have effective access to education and skill development which are invariable tools for a better socio-economic environment. A study carried out by the author at individuals belonging to this community, in and around Delhi reveals the pathetic and exploited condition of this vulnerable group. The study further exposes that the eunuchs are covert society; their social status makes them invisible. Still they could acquire certain kinds of skills even without professional training(s). But they have not been successful to come out from the existential trauma due to the prevailing attitude of disengagement of the mainstream society. An exploration to the hard realities of their lives...

Individual without Identity, Society without a social respect, citizen without headcounts, their claps are more vocal than their voices. At times they are respected as someone who can bless our newborns, sometimes suspected as looter at our marriage functions and on roads, mostly humiliated as sin at religious or social events but has never been accepted as just another one... just another soul.... just another creation of Nature... just another human. Yes, that is how we define Eunuchs in Indian labeled as *Kinners-Hiras*.

Ever since the inception of mankind, the entire society is represented by either male or female identity. Adam and Eve have never been conceptualized in any other sexual identity than this. To the best of our findings, no historian or scientist could ever find any sexual character or even they mentioned of it in the Ice Age. As per historians the understanding of gender identity evolved over the years, but Biological Science has been the key in recognizing 'transgender', though some reference has been found in mythological documents (Mahabharata and Ismat Chuktai).

Transgender is an umbrella term used to describe gender variant people who have gender identities, expressions or behaviors not traditionally associated with their sex at birth. The term transgender is preferred over older terms *transvestite* or *transsexual*, which do not accurately describe all transgendered people and also have a clinical or stigmatizing connotation. Transgender also can mean anyone who *transcends* the conventional definitions of 'man' and 'woman'. Thus transgender also can include many other kinds of gender variant people who use a variety of terms to self-identify.

However, it can take years to affect these physiological changes, as well as to adapt to new social roles. Transgender care is also commonly quite difficult to obtain, due to the lack of volunteering providers, the lack of health insurance coverage, and its expense. All of these realities tell how badly the transgendered people are treated in the modern society.

Population of Eunuchs

In the absence of a census conducted by a Indian Government, which could reflect an official figure of eunuchs at the state and national level, it is just not possible to reach at a definite number, but only an estimate. Eunuchs do not have family ties, so they prefer to migrate to places where they get better livelihood. Gurus also trade them off to places where earnings are higher. Therefore, they throng to Delhi, Kolkata, Chennai, Mumbai and other big cities.

Majority of the NGOs (NAAZ, SPACE, CSR) working in the field say that there are 25,000 eunuchs in Delhi. Most of the individuals and Deras claim their number is more than 75,000 in Delhi and NCR region. But they couldn't substantiate this claim. According to Things Asian, about 3,00,000 eunuchs live in Delhi.

It was in 2009 that eunuchs were allowed to enroll themselves and contest the MCD elections as 'others' instead of male or female. The move enabled the community to be part of the socio-political stage. Ballots were casted for 272 wards of the trifurcated MCD 15 April 2012. According to State Election Commission, there were a total of 1,15,20,508 - 64.42 lakh men and 50.75 lakh women - eligible voters. Voters

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Adult Continuing Education and Extension, University of Delhi.
² Associate Professor, Department of Adult Continuing Education and Extension, University of Delhi

in 'Other' category were just 35. Whereas it was Chandni, 27, is among the few eunuch candidates contesting the Municipal Corporation of Delhi (MCD) elections for the first time.

According to surveys carried out by Salvation Of Oppressed Eunuchs (SOOE), the number of eunuch in India is around 19 lakhs, as of March 1, 2011. Also it estimates the total number of transgender population in Delhi NCR is about 49,400, which seems to be in tune with majority claims. An attempt made by MCD to make a head count by virtue of the pension scheme launched in 2010 but fell apart.

Lastly, the Majority of Transgender confesses (Off the record) that in the entire NCR region, there is only one person who was born as eunuch, presently residing in West Delhi. The statement finds resonance across all sections, even within the community.

The research found that the majority of their earnings are either from *Tolli Badhai* (dancing and singing during the birth of a child) or prostitution or begging. Sporadic success stories of self-employed *Kinner*s who run food shops, or organize cultural programs are reported in some states. However, those were exceptions. Few of them were not very comfortable with the question about their earning and did not respond. One of them was a student. Majority of the eunuch who are illiterate are middle aged or elderly persons, people in the age group of 40 - 60 years. Most of the eunuchs with secondary or post-secondary level are young, 18-35 years of age. Few of them manage to reach university or college level and even fewer are lucky and brave to complete their studies successfully. Though more than half of their population is skilled but the level of skill is not very encouraging. Very few are professionally trained. Lack of opportunity makes it difficult for them to showcase or even polish their creativity. Further, skills that are directly affecting the earning capacity of a eunuch (*Kinner*) are minimal.

Gender of a Saint

In order to strengthen the work, efforts were made to meet such peoples at their places like *Deras*, Traffic signals where eunuchs usually beg and even on the specific location where they practice prostitution at night. *Sunitadidi*, an MCD Sweeper advised the researcher "Aap hizdoke mandir chaleyjao *Bhaiya*". What? Yes, that's right. "*Hizdo Ka Mandir*" (Temple of Eunuchs). When the researcher first heard the term, he was taken by surprise. Their religious practice of visiting Mosques, Mazars and Temples is well established fact. But researcher never had any introduction with this concept termed as "*Hizdo Ka Mandir*". Is it a place of worship only for Eunuchs? Or is it the temple of a God or Goddess worshiped by them only? The term might have been used at least fifty times, while locating of that temple, somewhere in *Sultan Puri*. There was a bit hesitance while using that sentence as this may be a derogatory remark for the community. But very soon research was comfortable with the phrase as nobody raised any objection to it.

It was above 40 Degree Celsius and driving in the narrow lane was adding up to the worry of a probable or rather forcible U-turn, in case it was misdirected. Soon researcher reached to a blood-red structure with a unique architecture, "*Hizro Ka Mandir*".

Researcher was introduced to the head priest *Banku*, an elderly eunuch in her late 80's. *Banku* has been living in Delhi for the last five decades and her spiritual description of eunuch's was nothing less than philosophical genius. A respected name across all sections of eunuch community, she is nothing less than a saint for rest of the society. She turned to spirituality at the age of 25, at a crucial juncture of life when all others were inclining to either *TolliBadhai* or sex work.

"Why eunuchs are to be considered as human being with holy blessings? This is what I asked myself" said *Banku*. "What if we do not surrender to *Kaam* (sex), as biologically we are not designed for that by Him?" The search for the answer to these questions transformed *Banku* a eunuch to *mataji*, a mother like cult figure for the society, a Saint.

"All human suffer four disorders in their acts and behavior. *Kaam*, *Krodh*, *Lobh* and *Moh* (Sexuality, Anger, Greed and Affection)" *Banku* added. "And by default a true eunuchs is detached from three of them *Kaam*, *Lobh* and *Moh* (Sexuality, Greed and Affection). It is easier for us to attain salvation as we just have to overcome one aberration, our anger"

She might not be in good health today, but she has proven her point that Eunuchs too can live another day, but for knowledge.

Another, eunuch (anonymous identity) who is living not for her own sake, but for the sake of a two-month old girl child, forced us to think other-wise, against the social definitions and descriptions about them. "Her mother sacrificed and breathed to give her the first soufflé. Abounded by her alcoholic father, a girl was not choice for the rest of the family. But, God has assigned me for her upbringing", and she added further "I will do it as a part of my duty, not as charity."

In India, both central and state government has been silent on the issues to the extent that they still face an identity crisis on records. So despite the fact that situation is grave and oppression faced by Hijras Transgender communities is the fact of the day where relief is a distinct possibility, task of understanding the life of TGs is frailly simple to start with. There are some straight conclusions that can be drawn from research conducted by the author (Delhi and NCR)

- a) Majority of the eunuchs living in Delhi are Illiterate (35 %) or semi-literate (60 %).
- b) Most of them are unskilled or semi-skilled. Here it is important to mention that percentage of professionally trained or high skilled eunuch is minimal.
- c) Largely, level of education or skill acquired by eunuch does not help them earn better. This is because most employers deny employment for even qualified and skilled transgender people. Lack of livelihood options is the key reason for significant proportion of Kinners to choose Deras or continue in Sex work.
- d) They are highly disproportionate in their earning capacities. Some of them own high asset values and have high income (above Rs. 50,000 per month), whereas some barely survive on less than 50 rupees a day. By and large majority of them manage to put up 6,000-10,000 per month. These are the eunuch living in Dera Culture.
- e) Kinners of Delhi are by-polar religious groups, either Hindu or Muslim. Surprisingly most of the eunuch practicing Islam lives in and around East Delhi region (Shahadra, Selemipur, BhajanPura, SeemaPura etc.) along with other parts of the city.

Diversity in a community also means the conflict of interest, conflict of ideas and even conflict of identities. They have huge differences over personal, profession and religious issues. Though it is difficult to comment on how they resolve their disputes but they do not approach the Law for inter-community conflicts. They have a self-regulatory system for sure. They also have well drafted system to choose Guru (successor) in a Deras.

All though few groups have strong professional revelries regarding their areas for Tolti Bhadhai, least interaction is witnessed when it comes to religion. Efforts are made by the community itself to draw rule and guideline to avoid religious and professional clashes. Majority of the Eunuchs living in Delhi can be divided into groups and sub groups such as;

- i. Those living with Deras and
- ii. Those living out of Deras (either alone or with family)

This is the only and most visible distinction in the community. Thought the conduct of the present generation is more or less the same as that of the earlier one, but they are better educated for sure. Today they have a choice to move between Gays (Educated, sophisticated, well-to-do people, campaigning MSM) and eunuchs (asking auspicious money, Indulged in sexual activities to earn livelihood).

A large section of the social workers believe that being eunuch is a state of mind and has nothing to do with sexual character i.e. all Eunuchs are transgender but all transgender are not necessarily Eunuchs, where as other disown these kind of explanation. Dera sections argue that the gay phenomena and gays are being misused to defame eunuchs and earn money using their social status. State Government recommend only the medical test done at a government hospital to recognize the identity of a Eunuch (eunuch). Hence, as there is no definite method, ways or means to define a Eunuch, getting an official figure about them is a distant dream the community has yet to archive a consensus in coordination with state authorities. For as of now we have two degrees of distinctions

(i) Eunuch by sympathy

(ii) Eunuch by choice

Almost every Eunuch follows a descending track of social respect in society. He starts his career from the center of a social structure and is gradually pushed out of it. The acts of social and moral exclusion are being to him, just as he is being pushed out of the social structure. The eunuch is a person who is being pushed out of the social structure down with given social status. Presumably they are one of the least deserving members of the society.

It is a truly liberal and authoritarian society, a group defined by its own rules and self-interest. It is with discipline. The statement is true at least for those following their culture. Presumably they are good enough to meet their daily needs. They live a better economic condition than it could be for some groups living in the city. All their acts are not governed by their appetite.

The community is least exposed to the rest of the society, and they themselves are being blamed for it. They are least interested in any kind of interaction with the other section of the society. One needs to do some arguments and fabricated stories roaming in the society. Our age old judicial system and untrained police force treat them as abuse. Police use IPC 377 against eunuchs, which is a section without law and which can get them a jail term from six months to seven years. A legal petition against this practice is pending in the Supreme Court. It is a blank page in our law book, waiting for a draft reflecting the rights and duties of Eunuchs.

Like many other diversities they have a huge bandwidth reflecting education and skill level of Eunuchs. It ranges from illiterates to Post-graduates. I am yet to see a doctorate in the community. Earlier people were forced to leave the school even at the primary stage, if at all they manage to get admitted to one. Today as gay culture is quite visible in our society, the resistance has drastically reduced in the last two decades. Some sections specially females has started recognizing them as just. This very thought has helped in retaining them in educational institutions. But the above mentioned data shows that level of education of a Eunuch is not directly proportional to his earning, as long as he maintain his identity as Eunuch.

Employment opportunities are very rare. Most public and private companies give several excuses to deny employment. The end result is that they are forced into Devax, begging or prostitution. People who scroll at the hijras during daylight approach them for perverted sex. Most of the eunuchs are forced to offer sexual service to such perverted minds for their daily bread. Most of the hijras end up having various sexually transmitted diseases including AIDS.

They are a community keeping pace with the time. We should appreciate them for treating the birth of a girl child as an event of celebration. This might give them one more dimension to earn money, but let's appreciate this gesture as mean and not as the final intention. They have been volunteers in AIDS awareness programme (s) and campaign run by state and social networking groups.

"They are born with a past and to try to be themselves of that past is to deform their present relationship". "What is at stake is the respect for individuals' autonomy and equality under law. At stake is an individual right to liberty, choosing the position in space and time."

The Research has been a voyage to realize that "In real sense, there two partners of a Human identity, first is the person who own it and second is the approving state or society"

Making recommendations is revising principals in the light of new findings. Also solutions suggested to meet the most immediate problems, may not be absolute in nature. Base on the research, the most immediate steps that can instigate the process of change in Eunuch community are;

- We need to disassociate them from other Transgender at large. This will not only lead to polarised efforts to find specific solution, but will also disassociate them from sidelining issues like gays and lesbian rights movements.
- Society should talk to them, rather than talking about them. They should be called upon to express their views.

- Many more in-depth researches are the need of the hour in order to have a better understanding of different aspects of "eunuch". A participatory research is recommended.
- Education is important, but as of now it should be projected as tool to self-assistance and not only as an end with self-reliance. An integrated approach is to be adopted to educate them as per their needs. For this a study need to be carried out to understand their present status in detail, also a focus on strengths and weaknesses about learning needs, and skill required to make them self-dependent.
- Special Skill Development programme(s) need to be designed, followed by some financial scheme (Like SSI) to help them sustain as Self Help Group or Cooperative Group.
- The threshold between Deras and the society has to be diluted. This does not mean that they should be dragged out of Dera or dismantle Deras. A sudden breakdown of this cultural practice may lead to disaster.
- Ways and means are to be discussed to establish a bench mark, not to isolate them as an identity but to fortify their self-respect.
- Gays should talk about Eunuchs more openly. They need to voice their(Eunuchs) concern.
- Society should encourage them to join main stream jobs, so that educated youth (Gays, Crossed-dressed and other transgender) does not fall back to Dera culture.
- Need is to establish few (learning) centers where they can hangout, do all kind of fun activities, have access to some reading material, an information window, basic medical services available, internet access etc. and most importantly a structure without veil which is accessible to all.

What's required is, Respect for our fellow citizens, eunuch's moral and religious conviction not by ignoring but by engaging them, by attending to them. Sometime by challenging and contesting them, sometime by listening and learning from them. There is no guaranty of any given case of agreement or even appreciation, for and religious conviction of others, it is always possible after all learning more will lead us to light. But the respect for the liberation and engagement seems to be a more ideal for a pluralistic society for eunuch.

Justice is a matter of giving people what they deserve. Today it has to be detached from questions of moral rights and virtue. In reasoning about Justice and right we have unavoidably to reason about the purpose or the end of social practices and institutions. Yes, the idea of equality is at the core of recommendation, but equal in what respect? That is what needs to be established. It is not about income and wealth, but about offers and honors.

REFERENCES

- APCOM Report No. 2. (2008). South Asian Transgender Groups, Organizations and Networks REPORT
- APCOM Report. (2008). Mapping Transgender Groups, Organisations and Networks in South Asia No. 2.
- Chakrapani, V, Babu, P, Ebenezer, T. (2004).Hijras in sex work face discrimination in the Indian health-care system. Research for Sex Work.
- Danielou, A. (1994). The Complete Kama Sutra. The first unabridged modern translation of the classic Indian text by Vatsyayana. Thomson Press (India) Ltd: Mumbai.
- From 2003-2009, the NEXUS Research Unit, based at the University of British Columbia and provincially funded by the Michael Smith Foundation for Health Research (MSFHR).
- Gaye, Amie. (2010). Human Development Research Paper 2010/46: Measuring Key Disparities in Human Development: The Gender Inequality Index. UNDP, 1-41. http://hdr.undp.org/fr/rapports/mondia/rdh2010/documents/HDRP_2010_46.pdf (Accessed on Dec. 8, 2010)
- Gender Education and Advocacy. (2001). Inc.
- Gender Education and Advocacy. (2001). Inc.

Gender.org, Hot Seated question about transgender people

Gwendolyn Ann Smith and Ethan St. Pierre Data, A product of Gender Education & Advocacy
HRLN Compendium Part-6

Intersex Society of North America (ISNA)

Jaggi (prem Nagar), Sumita MCD (Delhi Government)

Mapping Transgender Groups, Organisations and Networks in South Asia No. 2, July

Measuring Gender Inequality through Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) A Study of an Individual Case from an Islamic Society Submitted To: Dr. Satyajit Singh, Dept. of Political Science, School of Social Sciences, University of Delhi Submitted By: Rijaya Kumar Mohanty (Ph.D. Scholar)

Nanda, Serena. (1990). Neither Man Nor Woman: the Hijras of India, Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Publishing.

National AIDS Control Organisation (NACO). (2006). Strategy and Implementation Plan - National AIDS Control Programme Phase III [2007-2012]

National AIDS Control Organization (NACO). (2007). HIV sentinel surveillance and HIV estimation in India: technical brief. New Delhi, NACO, 2007. Available at: http://www.nacoonline.org/upload/Publication/M&E%20Surveillance,%20Research/HIV%20Sentinel%20Surveillance%20and%20HIV%20Estimation%202007_A%20Technical%20Brief.pdf

Ranade, S.N. Social Welfare Report, Ministry of Social Welfare, Government of India.

Salvation of Oppressed Eunuchs (SOOE)

Sex Reassignment Surgery (SRS).

Social Institutions and Gender Index Website: <http://genderindex.org/content/social-institutions.co.in>

The Intersex Society of North America (ISNA)

TRANSGENDER WORKPLACE DIVERSITY by Jillian T. Weiss J.D., Ph.D

UNAIDS and SAATHI, Calcutta

United Nations. (2007). Theoretical concepts of social exclusion. Chapter 1. In: Literature review on social exclusion in the ESCWA region. New York, NY: United Nations, 2-7. TG Issue
